

First semidwarf boro rice (*Oryza sativa*) germplasm collected in eastern Uttar Pradesh, India, breeds true

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Traditional boro rice is a unique type of *Oryza sativa* grown during the winter season (minimum temperature around 4 °C) in the depressions around rivers and lakes. A project funded by the Uttar Pradesh (UP) Council of Agricultural Research was undertaken to collect and conserve this type of rice. Twelve districts were explored and 570 accessions were collected. A semidwarf accession of traditional boro rice was spotted in the field of farmer Ram Briksha of Jhungiya village in the Baghauli block of Sant Kabir Nagar District, eastern UP, India. Collected in May 2000, this was given accession number 52. Plant height appeared to be about half that of a normal traditional boro plant. The average plant height of the semidwarf accession is 54.6 cm, while a tall plant without fertilizer is above 119 cm. The semidwarf plant has the same number of internodes, but the internode length was reduced. The lower internodes were much shorter than normal.

From October 2001 to May 2002, the entire collection was grown for categorization and cataloguing using the traditional package of practices. Observations on 22 morphoagronomic characters were recorded. Accession number 52 had 50 plants and all plants were semidwarf—i.e., they bred true. IRRI's *Standard evaluation system for rice* was used to describe the accessions:

Plant height	54.6 cm	Lemma and palea 3 (hairs on up- pubescence per portion)
Panicle length	16 cm	Lemma and 9 (black)
No. of grains per panicle	57	palea color
Days to 50% flowering	158	Spikelet fertility 3 (fertile)
Days to maturity	188	Heat tolerance 1 (<80% spike- let fertility)
Vegetative vigor	5 (normal)	The traditional boro rice plant
Seedling height	13.16 cm	is susceptible to lodging because
Cold tolerance	3 (seedlings light green)	of its poor culm strength and ex-
Leaf blade color	2 (green)	cessive culm length. Because of its
Leaf blade pubescence	2 (intermediate)	short culm, the semidwarf plant
Leaf length	26.0 cm	does not lodge. Fearing lodging
Leaf width	0.72 cm	problems, farmers do not add fer-
Basal leaf sheath color	3 (light purple)	tiziers that will further increase
Tillering ability	5 (medium, 10–19 tillers plant ⁻¹)	the chances of lodging and there-
Awn color	3 (brown, tawny)	by decrease yield. Thus, they
Awning	5 (short and fully awned)	continue to look for a semidwarf
Apiculus color	3 (tawny)	boro but with its grain character
Culm length	38.6 cm	intact. There are numerous semi-
Panicle exertion	5 (just exerted)	dwarf rice varieties but none in
Culm strength	3 (moderately strong)	traditional boro. This accession
		therefore has immediate agro-
		nomomic application. We had grown
		about 50 plants, all of which were
		semidwarf. The grain characters
		were typically those of boro rice
		(see table). (International organi-
		zations may request the seed
		through NBPGR, New Delhi.)
	

Comparison between common traditional boro variety and semidwarf accession no. 52.

Character	Traditional boro	Accession no. 52 (semidwarf)
Vegetative vigor	Vigorous (3)	Normal (5)
Seedling height (cm)	24.7	13.16
Leaf length (cm)	36.9	26.0
Leaf width (cm)	0.94	0.72
Culm length (cm)	83.8	38.6
Culm strength	7 (weak)	3 (moderately strong)
Plant height (cm)	104	54.6